

Title of thesis

Predictors of low oxygen saturation after balloon atrial septostomy in patients with d-Transposition of Great arteries with intact ventricular septum and restrictive ventricular defect

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By

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Certificate of the Institute

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Introduction:

Transposition of the great arteries (TGA) is a lethal and relatively frequent malformation, accounting for 5% to 7% of all congenital cardiac malformations. The clinical situation that results from this cardiac anomaly is characterized by severe and life threatening hypoxemia early in life . Before the advent of cardiac catheterization and cardiovascular surgery,, about 30% of these infants used to die in the first week of life, 50% within the first month, 70% within 6 months, and 90% within the first year. Today, aggressive medical and surgical interventions in the neonate can provide >90% early and midterm survival and, for many patients, the prospect of a vigorous adolescent and adult life .The incidence is reported to range from 20.1 to 30.5 per 100,000 live births with a strong (60% to 70%) male preponderance. Ventricular septal defect [VSD] is seen in 34% of the cases and one third of the VSD's are small [less than 3 mm] and have little hemodynamic significance ^{1, 2, 3} .

Tissue hypoxia is the dominant physiologic abnormalities in TGA. The systemic arterial oxygen saturations are dependent intercirculatory mixing: the flow in TGA on which survival depends. The extent of intercirculatory mixing in TGA depends on the number, size, and position of the anatomic communications and on the total blood flow through the pulmonary circuit. In the neonate with an intact ventricular septum and a closed or closing ductus arteriosus, severe hypoxemia secondary to inadequate mixing at the foramen ovale level is usually present.

Early diagnosis and prompt therapy for the neonate with TGA/IVS[Intact ventricular septum] are critical. Effective palliative treatment of complete transposition was introduced by Blalok and Hanlon [1950] with their atrial septectomy. As a primary palliative procedure however this had a high morbidity and mortality ⁴ .

Balloon atrial septostomy [BAS] introduced by Rashkind and Miller ⁵ in 1966 is the first innovative non-surgical therapeutic modality in pediatric cardiac catheterization. It had revolutionized the management of patients with complete transposition of great

arteries and palliated most of the patients who had undergone the procedure⁶. Survival for the first month of life improved from 20% before septostomy was introduced to as high as 95% afterward³.

Balloon atrial septostomy improves the intercirculatory mixing. After a successful BAS oxygen saturation goes upto 60% or increases by 10% and interatrial gradient decreases below 2 mm Hg. The size of adequate ASD [atrial septal defect] created is usually above 4 mm though it was quoted upto 8-12 mm in different series⁷. Factors which determine the oxygen saturation after BAS in patients with d-TGA + IVS \ restrictive VSD are the adequacy of intercirculatory mixing and adequacy of pulmonary blood flow.

There is incomplete agreement on physiologic criteria for satisfactory post-balloon septostomy improvement. Obviously, clinical stabilization and decreased hypoxemia must occur. In spite of successful BAS, upto 20% of the babies don't show the improvement in saturation. Excluding poor technical performance, several anatomic and physiologic factors may be responsible for unsatisfactory improvement. Nevertheless, despite the presence of adequately sized anatomic communications, inadequate circulatory mixing and disappointing clinical improvement have been noted in some infants⁷. Intuitively, these patients are likely to have low pulmonary blood flow, related to anatomic or functional factors. However, these have not been well characterized in a prospective study. Early identification of these factors can have an impact on the definitive management of these patients and may identify a sub-set that will require very early surgical correction.

Aim Of the Study:

To identify factors associated with sub-optimal improvement of systemic saturation after Balloon atrial septostomy [BAS] in infants with d-TGA with intact septum \ restrictive VSD.

Material and methods :

Setup:

Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences [AIMS] is a tertiary care superspeciality medical college under Amrita University. The study was done in the department of pediatric cardiology, which is a well-equipped state of art department dealing with all varieties of pediatric and congenital heart diseases. AIMS has well established pediatric cardiology unit along with pediatric cardiovascular surgery department.

Study population :

All babies with the diagnosis of d Transposition of great arteries [TGA] with intact ventricular septum [IVS] or restrictive VSD [less than 3 mm] requiring balloon atrial septostomy from March 2007 to September 2008 were included in the study.

Sample size : Thirty babies[30] with the diagnosis of simple transposition were included in the study who had undergone balloon atrial septostomy

Nature of the study:

Analysis of the predictors of poor outcome of an intervention in a prospective hospital based open-labeled study

Inclusion criteria:

1. d-TGA with intact ventricular septum.
2. d-TGA with restrictive VSD (< 3 mm\ < 50% of aortic annulus)

Exclusion Criteria:

- d-TGA with large VSD (unrestrictive)
- d-TGA with associated additional significant cardiac abnormality like Coarctation of Aorta

Nature of the outcome:

- A. Good out come
- B. Suboptimum outcome

Definition of Suboptimum outcome

- In case of non-ventilated babies persistently low SaO₂ < 60% for > 24 hours after BAS. [Mean value of 24 hours and value > 50% of time present will be considered]
- In case of babies who required mechanical ventilation during the procedure the mean oxygen saturation < 60% 24 hours after the extubation will be taken into consideration.
- < 10% improvement in SaO₂ after BAS. In case of babies who required mechanical ventilation during the procedure the Mean oxygen saturation 24 hours after the extubation will be taken into consideration.
- Development of or persistence of metabolic acidosis.
- Need for initiation of PGE1 infusion.
- Need for urgent surgical intervention.

Consent : Informed written consent was taken from the parents about the study .

Data collection technique :

All babies had undergone detailed clinical and Echocardiography evaluation after diagnosis and reevaluation after septostomy by a trained pediatric cardiologist.

Specification of the Measurement of the echocardiographic parameters

Tricuspid annulus was measured in apical four chamber view . The maximum value obtained was recorded between the hinge points between septal and anterior tricuspid leaflet. Mitral annulus was measured in apical four chamber view. The maximum value obtained was recorded between the hinge points between anterior and posterior mitral leaflets. Pulmonary annulus was measured between the hinge points of pulmonary valve leaflets on parasternal long axis view .Aortic annulus was measured between the hinge points of aortic valve leaflets on parasternal long axis view with leftward sweep. Left ventricular posterior wall (LVPW) was measured in parasternal long axis view in M mode echo in the plane of the posterior mitral valve leaflet (PMVL) from the endocardial surface to the epicardial surface (or to anterior extent of the pericardial echo if epicardium were not clearly delineated) at the beginning of the QRS⁸ .

Equipments : The Echocardiography was done by PHILIPS Sono 5500 and PHILIPS iE33 machine. Oxygen saturation was checked by Spacelab 90309 PC SCOUT multichannel monitor and Nellcor Pulse Oximax N-65 Handheld Pulse Oximeter Kit [Manufacturer: Nellcor Puritan Bennett]

Procedure : Septostomy was done either in cardiac catheterizations laboratory [SIMENNS Cineangiography machine] or in Intensive Care Unit under echocardiographic guidance as per the clinical status of the baby

Variables analyzed:

No	Name of the variable	Nature of the variable
1.	Continuous variable	Age of the patient in days , Hemoglobin gm% , Pre and Post BAS ASD size, Mitral annulus in mm , Tricuspid annulus in mm , Mitral and tricuspid annulus ratio. Pulmonary annulus in mm , aortic annulus in mm , pulmonary and aortic annulus ratio, LV Posterior wall in mm, PDA in mm ,
2.	Discrete variables	Presence of restrictive VSD , Septal Configuration [1. Bulged to RA, 2. Flat], Pattern of shunting of ASD [Group 1. Left to right Group 2. Bi-directional], PDA shunting pattern [Group 1. Left to right Group 2. Bi-directional]

Statistical analysis :-

The data were analyzed with Microsoft office 2007 and SSPS statistical software. The Chi-Square test and Fisher Exact tests were used for discrete variables and independent student T test was applied for continuous variables in calculation of statistical significance. The independent student T test was chosen for continuous variables. In the univariate analysis none of the variables were found to be statistically significant hence multivariate analysis was not done. p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Literature Review

WILLIAM J. RASHKIND and WILLIAM W. MILLER⁹ studied 32 d TGA babies from 1965 to 1967, 21 with VSD or 7 without a VSD [7] or PDA {3} [total= 10] and BAS done in 31 patients the time of BAS ranged from 4 hours to 332 months (average, 28 days), and all but two weighed less than 9 pounds. Systemic arterial oxygen

saturation was measured before and immediately after BAS in 20 of the 31 patients. All 31 patients survived balloon atrioseptostomy without complications; 26 of them (84%) had effective immediate palliation, and 22 (71%) are long-term survivors. They found patency of the ductus arteriosus relatively common in infants with TGA, but it was rarely of hemodynamic significance. However three infants of TGA and PDA with a large L-R shunt with CCF at an early age and died within hours after emergency BAS. They suggested the PDA should be ligated, if CCF persists after BAS had provided adequate mixing. They stressed on general management. Effective digitalization and prompt diuresis for the TGA babies.

Neches W H et al ⁷ defined satisfactory BAS as increase saturation of 10% or arterial saturation more than 60%, ASD more than 8 mm and no gradient between atria. They observed up to 20% of babies didn't show improvement in saturation in spite of adequate BAS. Some of non-responders improved after 2-3 days. Remaining had some deficiency in Atrial mixing, not readily explainable might be due to preferential flow of pulmonary venous return towards Mitral valve.

Cherief A et al ¹⁰ studied the immediate effect of Rashkind's atrioseptostomy on systemic saturation in transposition of the great arteries (TGA). Thirteen neonates and infants (10 males and 3 females) with TGA underwent balloon atrial septostomy (BAS) at a median age of 20 days (range 2 and 60 days). The mean atrial septal defect diameter after BAS was 6.5 +/- 1.1 mm. The right ventricular saturation increased from 37 +/- 17% to 67 +/- 13% ($p < 0.001$). They found no correlation between the atrial septal defect diameter and the increase of systemic saturation after BAS. Whereas Baylen BG et al found the diameter of the foramen ovale was the primary factor influencing arterial oxygenation during prostaglandin infusion ¹¹. Baker et al ¹² found an initially adequate interatrial communication did not guarantee long-term satisfactory results.

Mok Q et al ¹³ assessed the outcome of balloon atrial septostomy in 102 infants with transposition of the great arteries (plus or minus associated anomalies) who underwent the procedure at their hospital in the 10 years from January 1975 to December 1984. They considered the procedure to have been unsuccessful if the patient died from any cause (including other surgical procedures) between the septostomy and subsequent interatrial repair (Mustard's operation) or arterial switch operation. Eighteen patients

died, although in only two was this as a direct result of the septostomy. Statistical analysis showed that low weight, presence of a persistent arterial duct, and Coarctation of the aorta were significant risk factors.

William G et al¹⁴ reviewed the factors contributing to or causing death before surgery in neonates with d- (TGA) despite anatomy suitable for the ASO [Arterial Switch operation] in to develop strategies to minimize preoperative attrition. 11 of 12 cases the cause of death was attributed to the sequel of profound hypoxemia from inadequate mixing. •Contributing factors were prematurely, 41.7%; severe respiratory distress syndrome, 25%; and PPHN [persistent pulmonary hypertension of newborn], 16.7%. They recommended prenatal diagnosis with delivery in a high-risk obstetrical unit with facilities for immediate BAS and supportive therapy for pulmonary hypertension and ventricular failure y to salvage this group of patients.

Leanage R et al¹⁵ analysed the fate of 144 TGA patients who had BAS [multivariate analysis]. Patients were withdrawn "alive" on reaching definitive surgery. The following largely independent factors were associated with a statistically significant excess mortality: pulmonary hypertension, the presence and size of a VSD Presence of persistent PDA, relative anemia, absence of LVOTO, low arterial oxygen saturation, aortic stenosis and Coarctation, BAS between 7-30 days. This prediction was correct in 76 per cent of the patients studied.

Waldman JD et al¹⁶ studied 81 babies with d-TGA + IVS and during initial BAS, PDA [Patent ductus arteriosus] was found with angiography in 39 of babies with significant shunt in 18 babies. In contrast to the usual clinical presentation of neonates with d TGA IVS, 12 of these 18 infants with a significant PDA had only slight cyanosis and 8 presented with tachypnea out of proportion to the degree of cyanosis. Acute early narrowing or closure, spontaneous (six infants) or surgically produced (three infants), occurred usually within the 1st month of life and was associated with a marked decrease in arterial oxygen saturation in eight infants, often with a rapid clinical deterioration

The palliation afforded by BAS to 124 infants with TGA was assessed by Powell TG et al¹⁷ in a study in terms of survival to 6 months of age without the need for further intervention. Prediction of success or failure in relation to palliation was significantly

affected by the presence of associated ventricular septal defect, left ventricular outflow tract obstruction, or persistent ductus arteriosus and by the maximum volume of balloon used to perform the septostomy. –There was a significant association between balloon volume and size of atrial defect found at subsequent surgery or necropsy.

Chantepie A et al¹⁸ studied –They studied the incidence and causes of preoperative deaths in isolated TGA. –199 TGA babies from 5 French centers were studied. 20 (9.9%) died before surgery. –The death was related to intracranial hemorrhage in one premature neonate, severe and early hypoxemia in 13 full-term patients (group A) and later sudden collapse in six patients (group B). Despite assisted ventilation (n = 13), bicarbonate infusion (n = 12), PGE1 (n = 7), inotropic drugs (n = 5) and BAS (n = 7), death occurred at 5 hr age. They concluded that the high preoperative mortality rate in isolated transposition of the great vessels was mainly due to absent or small Atrial shunt.

Sophie J¹⁹ reported Persistent fetal circulation as a cause of hypoxemia after BAS in a baby with d TGA. ECMO [Extra corporal membrane oxygenation] reversed PAH and ventricular insufficiency and preceded a safe, delayed, cardiac surgical procedure after the failure of immediate BAS and supportive therapy including Nitric oxide.

Kumar et al²⁰ studied all necropsies on patients with transposition of the great arteries who died at less than six months old between 1986 and 1991 at their institution. Of the 11 cases, five had a ventricular septal defect and six had an intact ventricular septum. The sections of the non-inflated lung, at least one section from each lobe, were studied histologically after staining with haematoxylin and eosin, trichrome, and elastic stains. Formal morphometric studies were not performed. In seven cases grade 0-1 Heath Edwards pulmonary vascular changes were present. One patient showed occasional foci of intimal proliferation. Three patients, aged six days, 10 days, and 3 5 months, showed unexpected advanced changes, significance had not been fully appreciated. Even though the pulmonary vascular lesions in the first two cases are classified as only grade 2, the findings suggested a progressive rather than reversible change. Severe occlusive intimal proliferation identified in the first week of life suggested that the smaller pulmonary arterioles had sustained a significant injury before birth. Two of our cases showed transient or no clinical improvement in oxygen saturation or effective pulmonary blood flow despite creation of anatomically satisfactory atrial communication. Intercirculatory

mixing or effective pulmonary blood flow in transposition is directly related to the amount of total pulmonary blood flow.' In the presence of pulmonary vascular disease the pulmonary blood flow will decrease, as will the effective pulmonary blood flow.

Although poor intercirculatory mixing in transposition of the great arteries can occur because of streaming effects,"³ They considered the possibility of pulmonary vascular disease in those cases of transposition without left ventricular outflow tract obstruction, who showed poor response to atrial septostomy.

We had analysed our retrospective data of balloon atrial septostomy in simple transposition of 41 babies between January 2005 to February 2007. Optimal result of BAS defined as post procedure oxygen saturation >60% with at least > 10% improvement after the procedure. The variables analyzed were demographics; presence of additional shunts small (< 2mm) patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) restrictive (<3mm) ventricular septal defects (VSD), size of atrial septal defect (ASD) before and after BAS, pulmonary artery annulus, aortic annulus and their ratio. 12 (29.3%) showed sub-optimal result. Presence of restrictive VSD (no sub optimal outcomes) or PDA (20.5% sub-optimal outcome) was associated with better outcome ($p<0.05$). There was no difference in demographic variables, ASD size before and after BAS in the two groups. There were no differences in the remaining clinical and echocardiographic variables between the two groups²¹.

Various studies showed different parameters being associated with the sub optimal results. Age, anemia, size of ASD and PDA, posterior wall thickness of left ventricle and pulmonary annulus: Aortic annulus ratio were linked with long-term outcome of post septostomy babies before arterial switch operation. There is paucity of prospective study, which has specifically dealt with the predictors of immediate out come of balloon atrial septostomy. This study will focus on the predictors of the poor outcome of balloon septostomy in prospective way to identify the poor responders so that babies who are not going to improve with BAS can be subjected to direct early surgery

Section III

RESULTS

Total number of patients [n= 30] **DIAGRAM :- I**

Good Outcome in 19 patients [TGA + IVS 16 babies, TGA +VSD 3 babies]

Suboptimal outcome in 11 babies [TGA + IVS 8 babies, TGA +VSD 3 babies]

Chart :- I Oxygen Saturation before and after BAS

SpO2	Total n=30		Good outcome n= 19		Sub Optimum n=11	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Pre BAS	63.42	10.41	65.49	8.72	59.52	12.28
Post BAS	78.54	9.54	81.34	8.91	73.26	8.68

Chart :- II Vital Statistics

Group Statistics						
Parameters	OUTCOME	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P Value
AGE in DAY 11.36 ± 13.36	Good	19	13.78	14.93	3.42	0.196
	Suboptimum	11	7.18	9.08	2.73	NS
WEIGHT in KG 2.81±0.35 kg	Good	19	2.76	0.33	0.07	0.323
	Suboptimum	11	2.89	0.39	0.11	NS
LENGTH in CM 48.82 ± 2.62 cm	Good	19	48.50	2.77	0.63	0.395
	Suboptimum	11	49.36	2.37	0.71	NS
BSA in M2 0.19 ±0.01 m2	Good	19	.1916	0.01	0.003	0.17
	Suboptimum	11	.1991	0.01	.004	NS

Chart :- III ECHOCARDIOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS

Parameters N=30, Mean \pm SD	Group Statistics [Independent T test]					P value
	OUTCOME	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
ASD Size Pre BAS 2.29 \pm 0.63 mm	Good	19	2.35	0.69	0.16	0.485
	Suboptimum	11	2.18	0.50	0.15	
ASD size Post BAS 6.42 \pm 1.36 mm	Good	19	6.42	1.38	0.31	0.977
	Suboptimum	11	6.44	1.40	0.42	
Mitral annulus 9.7 \pm 1.72 mm	Good	19	9.67	1.98	0.45	0.904
	Suboptimum	11	9.75	1.24	0.37	
Tricuspid annulus 11.68 \pm 2.28 mm	Good	19	11.37	2.52	0.58	0.363
	Suboptimum	11	12.18	1.78	0.53	
Mitral and Tricuspid annulus Ratio 0.84 \pm 0.14	Good	19	0.86	0.15	0.03	0.289
	Suboptimum	11	0.80	0.10	0.03	
Pulmonary annulus 7.58 \pm 0.94 mm	Good	19	7.56	0.99	0.22	0.881
	Suboptimum	11	7.61	0.89	0.26	
Aortic annulus 8.71 \pm 1.33 mm	Good	19	8.75	1.22	0.28	0.851
	Suboptimum	11	8.65	1.56	0.47	
Pulmonary annulus and aortic annulus Ratio 0.88 \pm 0.13	Good	19	0.87	0.12	0.03	0.634
	Suboptimum	11	0.89	0.15	0.04	
LV posterior wall 3.42 \pm 0.81 mm	Good	19	3.37	0.87	0.20	0.695
	Suboptimum	11	3.50	0.71	0.21	
Hemoglobin 14.51 \pm 1.93 gm%	Good	19	14.36	2.04	0.46	0.59
	Suboptimum	11	14.77	1.81	0.54	

Chart :- IV Arterial Blood Gas Parameters before and after BAS

Total population N=23 Mean ± SD	Group Statistics [Independent T test]					
	OUTCOME	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
PO2PRE 29.35 ±14.37 mm hg	Good	11	31.20	7.05	2.12	0.052
	Suboptimum	11	25.01	7.00	2.11	
PHPRE 7.11 ±1.2	Good	12	7.35	0.05	0.014	0.939
	Suboptimum	11	7.36	0.05	0.01	
BEPRE -5.63 ± 4.3	Good	10	-3.94	4.29	1.35	0.16
	Suboptimum	9	-6.88	4.43	1.47	
LACTPRE 5.51 ± 3.65 mmol/l	Good	10	6.10	4.72	1.49	0.49
	Suboptimum	10	4.92	2.61	0.82	
POSTO2 32.96 ± 9.74 mm hg	Good	8	41.92	10.39	3.67	0.003
	Suboptimum	10	28.60	5.79	1.83	
POSTPH 7.38 ±0.06	Good	12	7.41	0.10	0.02	0.623
	Suboptimum	11	7.39	0.05	0.017	
POSTBE -1.34 ±4.31	Good	9	-0.50	3.20	1.06	0.377
	Suboptimum	9	-2.38	5.32	1.77	
POSTLACT 3.98 ±1.24 mmol/l	Good	11	2.88	1.45	0.43	0.039
	Suboptimum	9	4.23	1.23	0.41	

PO2PRE: Pre BAS partial pressure of oxygen in artery in mm hg

PH PRE: Pre BAS arterial pH , BEPRE : Pre BAS arterial base excess, LACTPRE: Pre BAS arterial Lactate in nmol/l, POSTO2: Post BAS arterial pO2 in mm hg, POSTPH: Post BAS arterial pH, POSTBE: Post BAS arterial Base excess, POSTLACT: Post BAS arterial Lactate in nmol/l

Chart :- V Significance of variables for outcome

Variable	Description	p value	Significance
		Fisher Exact	
Basic cardiac Diagnosis	TGA + IVS [n=24] TGA + Restrictive VSD [n=6]	0.641	Not significant
Sex of Baby	Male [n=23], Female [n=7]	0.372	Not significant
BAS method	Fluroguided [n=28] Echo guided [n=2]	0.126	Not significant
Atrial septal configuration	Flat septum [n= 27], Septum bulged to right [n=-3]	0.279	Not significant
ASD shunt Pre BAS	Left to right [n= 23] , bi-directional [n=7]	1.00	Not significant
ASD shunt post BAS	Left to right [n= 18] , bi-directional [n=12]	0.266	Not significant
VSD size	Absent [n=24] , Less than 3 mm [n=6]	0.641	Not significant
PDA size Pre BAS	Less than 2 mm [n= 18], More than 2 mm [n= 5]	0.80	Not significant
PDA Pre BAS	Present [n=23], absent [n=7]	1.00	Not significant
PDA shunt Pre BAS	Left to right [n= 22] , bi-directional [n=1]	0.74	Not significant
PDA size post BAS	Less than 2 mm [n= 216], More than 2 mm [n= 2]	0.86	Not significant
PDA Post BAS	Present [n=23], absent [n=7]	0.372	Not significant
PDA shunt post BAS	Left to right [n= 22] , bi-directional [n=1]	0.72	Not significant

Results:

From March 2007 to September 2008 forty six [46] babies were admitted with a diagnosis of Transposition of great arteries [TGA] where balloon atrial septostomy [BAS] was done. 31 patients fulfilled the criteria of the study and were taken. One of the babies was found to have VSD 4 mm instead of initially reported 3 mm hence the baby was excluded from the study. Finally thirty babies were analyzed. Six babies had TGA along with restrictive ventricular defect [VSD]. 24 babies were having TGA with intact ventricular septum. Six babies had TGA with restrictive VSD [VSD < 3 mm]. Nineteen babies [63.3%] babies fulfilled the criteria for optimal response to balloon atrial septostomy [BAS]. Eleven babies [36.7%] showed suboptimal response as described in Diagram :I. The basic cardiac diagnosis did not have any significant influence in the outcome of BAS [p= 0.641].

The clinical status of the babies stabilized after the balloon atrial septostomy though the different variables were not statistically significant in the two subgroups of babies. The oxygen saturation was increased from 63.42 ± 10.41 % to 78.54 ± 9.54 % as a whole. The pH increased from 7.1 ± 1.2 to 7.36 ± 0.06 and the lactate changed from 5.51 ± 3.65 to 3.98 ± 1.24 . Even in the suboptimum response group the oxygen saturation increased from 59.52 ± 12.28 % to 73.26 ± 8.68 %. The Po₂ and Lactate was better in the good outcome group which was statistically significant [pO₂ = p 0.003 and Post Lactate p= 0.039] .

The age, sex, weight and length of the babies in the two subgroups of the babies was not significantly different [Chart II]. The method of BAS also did not have any impact on outcome.

Nine echocardiographic parameters were studied and they were statistically not significant to predict the suboptimum response to BAS. [CHART III] .

Neither the atrial septal configuration nor the shunting pattern in the ASD or PDA was predictive of outcome after BAS [Chart : IV,V] . The presence or absence of VSD also had not influenced the outcome in a statistically significant way .

Discussion :

Balloon atrial septostomy had modified natural history of babies diagnosed with transposition of great arteries. Survival for the first month of life improved from 20% before septostomy was introduced to as high as 95% afterward. In TGA, this

increased level of pulmonary blood flow will result in improved intercirculatory mixing and systemic arterial oxygen saturation, assuming that an adequately sized and favorably placed anatomic opening was created³ .

. The balloon atrial septostomy helped to stabilize the babies in sick state , prepared them for the definitive repair . The satisfactory BAS was defined in literature as increase in saturation 10% or arterial saturation more than 60% in the background of good atrial defect creation [4to 8 mm in different studies]^{7,9} . In the present study the aim of a good septostomy was defined as not only to improve the saturation of the baby but also to stabilize him clinically as reflected correction of metabolic acidosis and no further need for urgent surgical intervention or institution of Prostaglandin infusion to improve the pulmonary blood flow and mixing. The suboptimal result by saturation criteria was found in upto 20% of cases in literature⁷ . The retrospective study conducted before institution of this index study found the suboptimal response in 29.26 % cases. The present study showed even a large proportion of babies with simple transposition [36.7 %] did not fulfill the criteria laid down for an optimum BAS. There was no difference in the babies in the suboptimal result group in respect to age at the time of BAS , weight , length , sex. The presence of PDA or VSD was showed improving the outcome of BAS in earlier studies²¹ . which was not found in the present study though presence of PDA was associated with better oxygen saturation and clinical status in a study by Waldman JD et al¹⁶ . The size of atrial septal defect created also did not significantly differed in two subgroups as found by earlier authors^{10,12,21} . There was no difference in the shunting pattern of the different cardiac shunts which will predict the suboptimum outcome. The literature available in the balloon atrial septostomy mainly deals with the long term outcome or mortality^{13,14,15} ,. The immediate optimum result of BAS was not studied well. The retrospective analysis of BAS²¹ had highlighted some aspects and framed the origin of the present study.

The present study was proposed to find the determinants of suboptimum outcome after BAS so that the specific subgroup of babies could be identified before septostomy and those babies could be subjected to early surgical intervention. Mixing of blood and effective pulmonary blood flow are the two determinants of oxygen saturation in simple transposition of great arteries. The present study included various parameters like assessment of annulus of all cardiac vales and LV posterior wall

thickness in diastole . Ratio of the annuli was studied to give more objectivity to the parameters. The parameters did not differ in the babies with suboptimum outcome in compared with optimum outcome group. The same result was seen in the retrospective study²¹ . The atrial septal configuration bulged to right or flat pre BAS also did not predict the outcome though theoretically bulged septum to right should be better candidate for BAS predictive of high LA pressure . All the parameters studied in this study could not be predictive of suboptimum outcome. The LV posterior wall thickness of mm was found having better result after BAS. The fact which was not supported in the present study. Various causative factors were cited for suboptimum response to balloon atrial septostomy in simple transposition where an adequate interatrial communication is assured . When the interatrial or interventricular shunting sites are of adequate size, the level of arterial oxygen saturation is influenced primarily by the pulmonary-to-systemic blood flow ratio, with a high pulmonary blood flow resulting in relatively high arterial oxygen saturation. If the pulmonary blood flow is decreased by subpulmonary or pulmonary stenosis or elevated pulmonary vascular resistance, the arterial oxygen saturation will be lowered, despite adequately sized anatomic shunting sites³ .

Streaming pattern of blood flow and high pulmonary artery resistance were cited by various authors. Kumar et al²⁰ opined the possibility of pulmonary vascular disease in those cases of transposition without left ventricular outflow obstruction, who showed poor response to atrial septostomy after necropsy analysis of lung histopathology of transposition babies who had undergone BAS. Though these facts were also supported by other authors³ the overall percentage of cases where suboptimum response due to high PVR state was cited as 6-8% which can't explain the suboptimum results in a significant percentage of babies.

The present study had not specifically indicated any factors which were or were associated with suboptimum outcome .

In the neonate with IVS, the systemic arterial pO₂ may be as low as 15 to 25 mm Hg at presentation, with resultant anaerobic glycolysis and severe metabolic acidemia. Inevitably, unless intracardiac mixing is improved by palliative or corrective intervention, severe hypoxemia results in advanced acidemia,

hypoglycemia, hypothermia, and eventual death³. Though 36.7% babies did not full filled the criteria of successful BAS but their clinical status stabilized after the procedure.. The tachypnea and respiratory distress settled and the lactate pH improved. From sick These babies became stable patient for the definitive repair at 10-14 days of age.

Conclusion:

Transposition of great arteries is amongst one of the common cyanotic congenital heart disease which presents after birth . Balloon atrial septostomy stabilizes the babies by improving the intercirculatory mixing and improving oxygen saturation. This study analysed the predictors of suboptimum results after BAS . None of the variables analysed was statistically significant enough to predict the suboptimum out come. Though a significant proportion [36.7%]of the simple transposition babies had suboptimal results , maximum number of babies stabilized hemodynamically and metabolically and eventually became better candidate for arterial switch operation.

Limitation of the study.

- Number of the babies recruited was relatively small to draw statistical conclusion.
- Inter echocardiographar bias in measuring the echocardiographic parameters which was subjective
- The valve annulus and ratio of two valve annulus is a crude measure of relative size of the corresponding ventricle.
- Effective ventricular output could not be measured. Assessment b y three dimensional echocardiography of the ventricular volume and output can shed new light in future.
- Pulmonary pressure was not measured as the babies were in sick state. The opinion regarding occurrence of high pulmonary vascular resistance state could not be answered in the study.

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